

DCH Project Data Storage Guidelines

Version 1.0.0

1. Keep three instances
2. Keep two local instances on different media
3. Keep one off-site copy
4. Automatize data replication and backup
5. Document procedure and responsibilities

1 Three instances

Keep three instances of the data. Besides the original working instance, keep two copies of your project data.

2 Two local instances on different media

Keep two local instances of the data on different media. For example, keep your original working instance on the SSD of your computer and a copy on an external storage medium, a local NAS, or a network drive.

Example at the University of Cologne: [SOFS online storage](#)

3 One off-site copy

At least one instance of the data should be kept off-site so that localized incidents do not affect all copies of the data.

Example at the University of Cologne: [TSM backup system](#)

4 Automatize data replication and backup

The process of regular local replication and off-site backup should be automatized. The frequency of replication and backup must be adjusted to the maximum acceptable amount of data loss in case of an incident.

Example solutions: [TSM](#), [TimeMachine](#) (Mac only), [restic](#)

5 Document procedure and responsibilities

Document the data storage procedure – including location of the three copies, frequency of replication and backup – as well as the responsibilities for implementing the procedure e.g. in your data management plan.